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GENERALIZED PROCESS CAPABILITY INDEX APPLIED TO POISSON PROCESS DISTRIBUTION

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Abstract

Maiti et al.(2010), defined a Generalized Process Capability Index (GPCI) C_{py} that is based on the ratio of proportion of specification conformance to proportion of desired conformance of the process under study and has several appealing features. One of its advantages is that it can be used not only for continuous processes, as in the case with majority of the indices considered in the literature, but also for discrete processes which are frequently considered in statistical process control. This paper aimed at evaluating the index C_{py} for Poissin distribution. The well-known maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) is used to estimate the parameter. The bootstrap confidence intervals are considered in this paper consists of various confidence intervals. Three bootstrap confidence intervals -standard, percentile and bias corrected are compared based on average width and coverage probability.

Keywords: Poisson distribution, process capability index, maximum likelihood estimate, bootstrap confidence interval.

1. Introduction: Capability indices are frequently used when performing a capability analysis of a manufacturing process. Such indices based on the process parameters and the process specifications provide in just one number a measure of the ability to satisfy quality requirements. Capability indices have been widely dealt with in numerous articles and several books such as Kotz and Johnson (1993), Kotz and Lovelace (1998). Excellent reviews on them are given by Kotz and Johnson (2002). In addition, Spiring et al. (2003) and Yum and Kim (2010) provide an extensive bibliography on process capability indices. The vast majority of the process capability indices that have been considered are associated only with processes that can be described through some continuous and in particular normally distributed characteristics. The most widely used such indices are C_p (Juran, 1974), C_{pk} (Kane, 1986), C_{pm} (Chan et al., 1988) and C_{pmk} (Pearn et al., 1992) or their generalizations for non-normal processes, suggested by Clements (1989), Pearn and Kotz (1994 – 95). However, often, one is faced with processes described by a characteristic whose values are discrete. In such cases none of these indices can be

used. To our knowledge, the only indices suggested so far whose assessment is meaningful regardless of whether the studied process is discrete or continuous are those suggested by Yeh and Bhattacharya (1998), Borges and Ho (2001), Perakis and Xekalaki (2002) and Maiti et al. (2010).

A very common example of a process that can be described through a discrete-valued characteristic is the number of defects per produced unit by an industry. In this case, it is obvious that small process values are desirable. However, large values may also be desirable. As we have already mentioned, Maiti et al. (2010) proposed a GPCI, which is the ratio of proportion of specification conformance to proportion of desired conformance, can be used regardless of whether the examined process is continuous or discrete. The GPCI is defined as

$$C_{py} = \frac{P}{p_0}. \quad (1.1)$$

Where, $p = F(U) - F(L)$ and $p_0 = F(UTL) - F(LTL)$. U, L and UTL, LTL are upper specification limit, lower specification limit and upper tolerance limit, lower tolerance limit respectively. We know that the term proportion of conformance refers to the probability of producing within the so-called specification area, i.e., the interval determined by L and U . If the tolerances are unilateral, then the value of p is given by $P(X > L)$ and if only L has been set, and by $P(X < U)$ only if U has been set.

In this article, we consider only the GPCI C_{py} to measure the bootstrap confidence intervals (SB, PB, BCPB) for Poisson distribution. In the second section, we developed process capability index using maximum likelihood estimate (MLE) of the parameter of Poisson distribution. Here, we will focus on the development of bootstrap confidence interval, parametric estimation and GPCI for Poisson distribution. Bootstrap confidence interval for the GPCI C_{py} studied in the section 3. The simulation results for small sample comparisons are made in section 4 and some conclusions are made in the final section.

- 2. The index C_{py} for Poisson process:** As we have already mentioned, one of the advantages of the index C_{py} is that its assessment is possible even if the examined process is discrete. In this section, the properties of C_{py} are examined in the case where the studied process is described by a Poisson distributed characteristic with some parameter $\lambda > 0$. Under this distributional assumption, process yield p is given by

$$p = \begin{cases} P(L \leq X \leq U) \\ \sum_{x=L}^U \frac{e^{-\lambda} \lambda^x}{x!} \end{cases}$$

If the value is unknown, it has to be replaced by an estimate of it. The maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) of the parameter λ , provided that n independent observations X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n from the Poisson distribution with parameter λ are available, is given by

$$\hat{\lambda} = \bar{X} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i.$$

Substituting $\hat{\lambda}$ for λ , results the estimator of p as

$$\hat{p} = \sum_{x=L}^U \frac{e^{-\hat{\lambda}} \hat{\lambda}^x}{x!}.$$

Then, the MLE of the index C_{py} is given as

$$\hat{C}_{py} = \frac{\hat{p}}{p_0}. \tag{2.2}$$

Now, theoretically it is not possible to find out the exact sampling distribution of the estimator \hat{C}_{py} . Hence, a simulation study is made for small sample comparison.

3. Bootstrap confidence intervals: Bootstrap confidence intervals have been widely applied in estimating various PCIs. Suppose we find ourselves in the following common data analytic situation: a random sample $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ from an unknown probability distribution F has been observed and we wish to estimate a parameter of interest $\theta = t(F)$ on the basis of X . For this purpose, we calculate an estimate $\hat{\theta} = s(X)$ from X . How accurate is $\hat{\theta}$? The *bootstrap* was introduced by Efron (1982) as a computer-based method for estimating the standard error of $\hat{\theta}$. It enjoys the advantage of being completely automatic. The *bootstrap* estimate of standard error requires no theoretical calculations, and available no matter how mathematically complicated the estimator $\hat{\theta} = s(X)$ may be.

Given a sample of size m with sample values x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m we choose (with replacement) a random sample ([1], say) x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n of size n , and calculate $\hat{C}_{[1]py}$, from this new 'sample'. This is repeated many (g) times and we obtain a set $\hat{C}_{[1]py}, \hat{C}_{[2]py}, \dots, \hat{C}_{[g]py}$, which we regard as approximating the distribution of C_{py} in samples of size n - this estimate is the bootstrap distribution. (The theoretical basis of this method is that we use the empirical cumulative distribution from the first sample - assigning probability $1/m$ to each value - as an approximation to the true CDF of X .) Practice has indicated that a minimum of $B = 1000$ bootstrap samples are needed for a reliable calculation of bootstrap confidence intervals for C_{py} .

3.1 SB confidence intervals: Suppose 1,000 bootstrap samples are obtained by re-sampling from the observed values x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n (with replacement). The arithmetic mean \hat{C}_{py}^* and standard deviation $S^*(\hat{C}_{py}^*)$ of the \hat{C}_{py}^* are calculated. Then, $100(1 - \alpha)\%$ confidence interval for C_{py} is then given as:

$$\left\{ \hat{C}_{py}^* - Z_{1-\alpha/2} \cdot S^*(\hat{C}_{py}^*), \hat{C}_{py}^* + Z_{1-\alpha/2} \cdot S^*(\hat{C}_{py}^*) \right\}.$$

3.2 PB confidence intervals: The 1,000 \hat{C}_{py} 's are ordered as

$$\hat{C}_{py}(1), \hat{C}_{py}(2), \dots, \hat{C}_{py}(1000). \text{ The confidence interval is then given as: } \\ \{ \hat{C}_{py}([1000\alpha]), \hat{C}_{py}([1000(1-\alpha)]) \}.$$

3.3 BCPB confidence intervals: This is intended to produce a shorter confidence interval by allowing for the skewness of the distribution of \hat{C}_{py} .

Guenther (1985) pointed out the possibility of doing this in the general case, and Efron (1982) developed a method applicable in bootstrapping situations. The first step is to locate the observed \hat{C}_{py} in the bootstrap order statistics $\hat{C}_{py}(1) \leq \hat{C}_{py}(2) \leq \dots \leq \hat{C}_{py}(1000)$. For example, if we have $\hat{C}_{py} = 1.42$ from the original data, and among the, bootstrapped values we find

$$\hat{C}_{py}(365) = 1.41 \text{ and } \hat{C}_{py}(366) = 1.43,$$

Then, we estimate $P(\hat{C}_{py} \leq 1.41)$ as $\frac{365}{100} = 0.365 = p_0$, say. Then we calculate

$$\Phi^{-1}(p_0) = z_0 \text{ (i.e. } \Phi(z_0) = p_0).$$

Next we calculate $p_l = \Phi(2z_0 - z_{1-\alpha/2})$ and $p_u = \Phi(2z_0 + z_{1-\alpha/2})$ and form the confidence interval

$$\{ \hat{C}_{py}(1000p_l), \hat{C}_{py}(1000p_u) \}.$$

To study the different confidence intervals, we consider their estimated coverage probabilities and average widths. For each of the methods considered, the probability that the true value of the index C_{py} is covered by the $100(1 - \gamma)\%$ bootstrap confidence interval, which is called the ‘coverage probability’ can be obtained. In addition, the average width of the bootstrap confidence interval is calculated based on the 1000 different trials.

4. Simulation Results: We carry out a simulation study on the behaviour of three bootstrap confidence intervals of the process capability index defined in Equation (2.2) for Poisson distribution. In simulation study, we consider sample sizes $n = 10, 25, 50, 100, 150, 200$. In addition to these sample sizes, we set the lower and upper specification limits are 0 and 24 respectively. For each design, $B = 1000$ bootstrap samples with each of size n are drawn from the original sample. The 95\% bootstrap confidence intervals are constructed by each of the three methods, i.e., SB,

Figure 1: Comparison of average width of \hat{C}_{py} using SB, PB and BCPB method for different sample sizes and different values of parameter.

1. PB and BCPB confidence intervals. Table 1 reports the estimated average widths and coverage probabilities of 95% bootstrap confidence intervals of the index C_{py} for Poisson distribution.

From Table 1, note that, as the sample size increases, the average widths decrease in all the cases analysed for Poisson distribution as expected. Comparing the

average coverage probabilities, it is observed that for most of sample sizes, the coverage probabilities of the confidence intervals based on the each of the three methods (SB, PB and BCPB) results the nominal. Moreover, among the three methods of bootstrap confidence intervals the average widths of BCPB is least in most of the cases. Furthermore, with respect to average coverage probability, all the three methods show performance for large sample sizes and parametric values. Thus, based on simulation studies, the BCPB confidence intervals achieve better performance than other bootstrap confidence intervals for Poisson distribution.

Figure 2: Comparison of coverage probabilities of \hat{C}_{py} using SB, PB and BCPB method for different sample sizes and different values of parameter.

2. Conclusions: In this article, we have proposed bootstrap confidence intervals of capability index C_{py} , suggested by Maiti et al. (2010) studied through simulation study when the underlying distribution is Poission distribution. Three bootstrap confidence intervals are considered: the SB confidence interval, the PB confidence interval and BCPB confidence interval. The performances of bootstrap confidence intervals are compared by comparing their average widths and coverage probabilities. The parameter of the distribution considered in this article is studied with maximum likelihood estimation. Based on the simulation studies, the BCPB confidence intervals achieve better performance than the other bootstrap confidence intervals for Poisson distribution.

3. References

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Table 1: The estimated average widths and coverage probabilities of a 95% bootstrap confidence intervals of C_{py} for Poisson distribution.

n	θ	C_{py}	SB		PB		BCPB	
			Ave. Width	Cov. Prob	Ave. Width	Cov. Prob	Ave. Width	Cov. Prob
10	0:5	0.4141783	0.5303161	0.96700	0.4794826	0.96700	0.5652189	0.98800
25	0:5	0.4141783	0.3320791	0.96300	0.3192970	0.96300	0.3067772	0.94500
50	0:5	0.4141783	0.2552345	0.95900	0.2562418	0.96300	0.2371961	0.94900
100	0:5	0.4141783	0.1752603	0.96200	0.1664658	0.95700	0.1720441	0.96200
150	0:5	0.4141783	0.1404895	0.94800	0.1459995	0.95800	0.1401497	0.95600
200	0:5	0.4141783	0.1281284	0.94500	0.1323219	0.95600	0.1253709	0.95000
10	1.0	0.6653901	0.4801537	0.95000	0.4644545	0.96100	0.4352383	0.95000
25	1.0	0.6653901	0.2950055	0.95500	0.3056470	0.96900	0.2936624	0.96000
50	1.0	0.6653901	0.1881366	0.96400	0.1782484	0.95300	0.1747189	0.95200
100	1.0	0.6653901	0.1395333	0.94600	0.1369266	0.95300	0.1382256	0.95000
150	1.0	0.6653901	0.1150613	0.94500	0.1181232	0.95800	0.1111126	0.94500
200	1.0	0.6653901	0.1127225	0.94900	0.1148599	0.95400	0.1148599	0.95400
10	2.5	0.9662263	0.2443526	0.94400	0.2439680	0.96600	0.2207514	0.96100
25	2.5	0.9662263	0.0901650	0.96000	0.0862651	0.95700	0.0828826	0.95600
50	2.5	0.9662263	0.0854214	0.95200	0.0872567	0.95300	0.0838353	0.95300
100	2.5	0.9662263	0.0584501	0.95400	0.0575802	0.95600	0.0564400	0.95000
150	2.5	0.9662263	0.0416576	0.94800	0.0412491	0.95100	0.0412491	0.95100
200	2.5	0.9662263	0.0368727	0.94800	0.0372709	0.95300	0.0369001	0.95100
10	5.0	1.0455390	0.0181579	0.95900	0.0184109	0.96400	0.0165762	0.95400
25	5.0	1.0455390	0.0181199	0.96300	0.0171455	0.96000	0.0155398	0.95300
50	5.0	1.0455390	0.0096750	0.94600	0.0093177	0.95300	0.0093178	0.95300
100	5.0	1.0455390	0.0063611	0.95200	0.0063617	0.95500	0.0063172	0.95300
150	5.0	1.0455390	0.0050477	0.96000	0.0049831	0.95100	0.0048844	0.95000
200	5.0	1.0455390	0.0048904	0.94600	0.0048803	0.95200	0.0049586	0.95200